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O'quv jarayonini kompyuter imitatsion modellar asosida takomillashtirish metodikasi

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada jahon ta'lim tizimida elektron axborot-ta'lim resurslaridan foydalanib, fanlarning o'quv-metodik tahminotini takomillashtirish, ta'lim oluvchilarning kasbiy kompetentligini rivojlantirish, o'quv mashg'ulotlarida axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalaridan foydalanish metodikasi taxlil qilingan

Kalit so'zlar: elektron ta'lim, innovatsion bilim, imitatsion model, intellektual salohiyat, interaktiv ta'lim, metodika, elektron ta'lim.

Методология совершенствования образовательного процесса на основе компьютерных имитационных моделей

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Аннотация: В статье анализируется метод использования информационно-коммуникационных технологий в мировой системе образования, использования электронных информационно-образовательных ресурсов, совершенствования учебно-методической оценки предметов, развития профессиональной компетентности обучающихся, использования информационно-коммуникационных технологий в обучении.

Ключевые слова: электронное образование, инновационные знания, имитационная модель, интеллектуальный потенциал, интерактивное образование, методика, электронное образование.

Methodology for improving the educational process based on computer simulation models

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Abstract: The article analyzes the method of using information and communication technologies in the global education system, the use of electronic information and educational resources, improving the educational and methodological assessment of subjects, developing the professional competence of students, using information and communication technologies in teaching.

Keywords: electronic education, innovative knowledge, simulation model, intellectual potential, interactive education, methodology, electronic education.

Ma'lumki o'qitish metodlarida texnik vositalarni qo'llash yuqori o'rinda turadi. Texnik vositalar yordamida o'quvchilarga berilayotgan o'quv materiallarining hajmini oshirib borish, zamonaviy fan yutuqlarini kiritib borish imkoniyati yaratiladi. Yaqin vaqtlargacha texnik o'qitish vositalari sifatida kino va televideniya ta'lim tizimida katta yutuq sifatida qaralar edi. Ammo hozirgi vaqtda o'quv jarayonida kompyuter asosida modellashtirish muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Xuddi shunday kompyuter asosidagi imitatsion modellashtirish ham ta'lim tizimida muhim ahamiyatga ega. Tatbiq etilishi nuqtai nazaridan kompyuter asosidagi modellashtirish va imitatsion modellashtirish bir-biriga o'xshash vazifalarni bajaradi. Ya'ni obektni (ta'lim jarayoni nazarda tutilmoqda) ichki va tashqi xossalarini namoyon qilish imitatsiya yo'li bilan ko'rsatiladi.

Axborot texnologiyalarining jadal rivojlanishi zamonaviy o'quv jarayoniga innovatsion o'qitish usullarini joriy etish imkonini beradi, ular orasida kompyuter imitatsion modellari (KIM) alohida ahamiyatga ega.

Dunyo miqyosida ta'lim-tarbiya sifatini rivojlantirish, o'quvchilarda sog'lom turmush tarzi ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishning ijtimoiy-biologik va pedagogik-psixologik asoslarini tadqiq etishga oid ilmiy tadqiqotlar olib borilmoqda. Sog'lom turmush tarzi mazmunini o'zlashtirish imkonini beruvchi ilmiy yondashuvlar, shuningdek, ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonining innovatsion texnologiyalar hamda faol metod va vositalar asosida o'qitilishi o'quvchilarning sanogen tafakkurini rivojlantirishga xizmat qilmoqda.

Mamlakatning asosiy raqobatbardoshligi uning salohiyatini rivojlantirishga bog'liq bo'lib, u ta'lim tizimining sifati bilan belgilanadi. «Xalq ta'limi tizimiga ilg'or

xorijiy tajribani, o'quv-tarbiya jarayoniga zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalarni, shu jumladan, ta'lim berishning innovatsion usullarini joriy etish, o'quv va o'quv-uslubiy adabiyotlarning yangi avlodini yaratish, fundamental va amaliy ilmiy tadqiqotlarni amalga oshirish»[Travkin E.I., 2007] kabi muhim vazifalar belgilangan.

O'zbekiston Respublikasini yanada rivojlantirish bo'yicha Harakatlar strategiyasida belgilangan vazifalar asosida umumiy o'rta ta'lim sifatini tubdan oshirilishi, muhim va talab yuqori bo'lgan fanlar informatika, matematika, fizika, kimyo va biologiya fanlarini chuqurlashtirilgan tarzda o'rganishni tashkil etilishida fanlararo aloqadorlik va integrativ yondashuvdan foydalanish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Bu, o'z navbatida, biologiya fanining turli elementlari matematika, fizika, geografiya, kimyo kabi fanlarni o'qitish jarayonida qo'llaniladigan materiallar o'quvchilarning umumiy o'rta ta'lim predmetlari asoslarini o'zlashtirish darajasini oshirishning samarali texnologik vositasidir. Shuningdek, bu omil teskari aloqa printsipi asosida o'quvchilarga beriladigan biologik ta'lim samaradorligini oshirishga sezilarli tasir etadi. [Babkin E. A., 2005]

Respublikamizdagi ta'lim-tarbiya samaradorligini oshirish uchun audio, video va boshqa zamonaviy texnik vositalarni dars jarayoniga olib kirish, o'quv rejadagi asosiy o'quv fanlarini o'qitish jarayoniga kompyuter texnologiyasini joriy etishda o'qitishning interaktiv metodlarini ishlab chiqishga doir M.X.Lutfillaev, L.M.Qaraxonova, G.S.Ergasheva, B.M.Do'monov, F.M.Lutfillaeva va R.R.Eshimovlar tomonidan ilmiy tadqiqot ishlari olib borilgan.

Ta'limni axborotlashtirish jarayoni, atrofdagi voqelikni va uning turli xil predmetlari bo'yicha bilishning integratsiya tendentsiyalarini qo'llab-quvvatlaydi, o'quvchi shaxsini rivojlantirish uchun yangi axborot texnologiyalari imkoniyatlaridan foydalanishga turli uslubiy yondashuvlarni ishlab chiqish, bilim darajasini oshirish, ijodiy qobiliyat va tanqidiy fikrlashni rivojlantiradi.

Fanlarni o'qitishda axborot texnologiyalari vositalari va multimedia dasturlaridan foydalanish ham o'quv, ham amaliy masalalarning yechimlarini topish strategiyasini ishlab chiqish, jarayonni bashorat qilish va ta'lim muammolarini namunaviy yechish natijalarini tushuntirish uchun kompyuterdan foydalanish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish muhim vazifa hisoblanadi.

Kompyuter imitatsion modellar asosida yaratilgan virtual laboratoriyalardan foydalanish, o'quv jarayonini tashkil etish, o'quvchilarning ijodiy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish uchun yangi imkoniyatlar eshigini ochadi. Faol o'qitish usullarini samarali joriy etish uchun yetarli miqdorda kompyuter texnologiyasi bilan jihozlash, o'quv jarayonini tashkil etishda uslubiy va axborot bazasini tayyorlash bo'yicha jiddiy ilmiy-uslubiy ishlar olib borishni taqozo etadi.

KIM ishlab chiqishda fan o'qituvchilari, dizaynerlar, dasturchilar va psixologlardan iborat jamoa faoliyat yuritdi. KIM yaratishning muhim jihatlaridan biri qaysi mavzu bo'yicha imitatsion jarayonni to'liq va samarali ko'rsata olish masalasini muhokama qilish maqsadga muvofiqdir.

Xulosa qilib shuni aytish mumkinki bugungi kunda Respublikamizda ta'lim tizimini axborotlashtirish, dars jarayonida zamonaviy ta'lim texnologiyalarini qo'llash va o'quv jarayonida elektron ta'lim resurslaridan foydalanish hamda o'quv jarayoniga axborot texnologiyalarini qo'llash, kompyuter yordamida modellashtirish, elektron ta'limni joriy etish, ilg'or pedagogik va axborot texnologiyalarini rivojlantirish, virtual laboratoriya mashg'ulotlarini ishlab chiqish bo'yicha amaliy va nazariy ishlar olib borish kabi ishlar asosida umum ta'lim maktablari o'quv jarayonini samaradorligini oshirish masalalari muhokama qilingan.

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